

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE EDUCATIONAL COMICS IN CELL BIOLOGY TO IMPROVE THE METACOGNITION SKILLS OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS FROM CAVITE STATE UNIVERSITY-CCAT CAMPUS A.Y. 2024-2025

*Vince Jaron Hernandez*¹, *James Cajustin*², *Neila Cathlene Corona*³,
*John Marc Mejos*⁴, *Lawrence Salvador Nazareno*⁵

* rc.vincejaron.hernandez@cvsu.edu.ph ; 0009-0000-4957-6164

* rc.james.cajustin@cvsu.edu.ph ; 0009-0007-1286-9191

* rc.neilacathlene.corona@cvsu.edu.ph ; 0009-0008-0389-5475

* rc.johnmarc.mejos@cvsu.edu.ph ; 0009-0005-9905-6083

* rc.lawrencesalvador.nazareno@cvsu.edu.ph ; 0009-0001-3757-4687

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop science educational comics and evaluate their effectiveness in enhancing students' metacognitive skills in understanding abstract concepts in cell biology. A 20-item multiple-choice test was utilized to assess improvements in analytical thinking and reading comprehension, aligned with the objectives of the topics included in the comics. A Table of Specifications ensured the validity of the test items, and a survey questionnaire provided recommendations for future studies. A class of 22 respondents participated from Grade 7 in a Laboratory Science High School, with their consent. Data analysis revealed a significant improvement in students' understanding of abstract cell biology concepts after integrating the comics, with analytical thinking showing a greater increase than reading comprehension. Students reported that the comics facilitated their understanding of abstract concepts in cell biology. Future research should explore variations in comic style, content features, and applications in other fields of science.

Keywords: science educational comics; cell biology; metacognition

INTRODUCTION

For years, low science literacy has been a challenge among Filipino students (Martin, 2004). The PISA 2018 results show Filipino students scoring 357 points in science literacy, well below the OECD average of 489, indicating ongoing struggles in science education (Cordon and Polong, 2020). Teachers and

experts attribute this to poor-quality science textbooks, which fail to explain abstract concepts effectively (Irez, 2009). Cell biology, in particular, is often seen as one of the most difficult subjects for high school students (Sallah et al., 2021; Fauzi et al., 2018), with traditional lecture-based teaching methods focusing on content rather than engagement, limiting motivation and metacognition development (Akcanca, 2020; Çimer, 2012).

The PISA results present an opportunity for teachers to innovate and improve science literacy. According to Çimer (2012), using visual materials like educational comics can make cell biology learning more effective. Educational comics are affordable, engaging, and can simplify abstract concepts, making them a powerful tool in science education (Akcanca, 2020). Research by Badeo & Ong Kian Koc (2020) shows that comics-based learning modules improve students' conceptual understanding and motivation.

Many studies suggest that developing science educational comics can improve metacognitive skills, especially in cell biology. These comics combine engaging text and visuals to simplify complex concepts, like cell division and structure. Sequential visuals and captions break down topics such as mitosis and meiosis into clear, step-by-step segments, promoting active learning and self-reflection. Comics also use humor and engaging plots to make learning more enjoyable and effective than traditional textbooks.

This study focuses on creating a science educational comic to enhance students' metacognitive skills in cell biology. The comic aims to simplify abstract concepts and improve students' understanding compared to traditional text-based materials, making learning more engaging, fun, and effective.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a developmental research design, defined as the systematic study of designing, developing, and evaluating instructional programs, processes, and products that must meet criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness (Rita 1994). The researchers aim to evaluate the efficacy of science-

based educational comics in developing the metacognitive skills of students, specifically the analytical thinking and reading comprehensions, and its applicability to other sub-branches of general science. Throughout the course of conducting this study, the researcher initially developed science-based educational comics, whose topic circulates under general biology. Succeeding to that is the construction of questionnaires, which will then be distributed to 22 participants from Grade 7 of Laboratory Science High School

Testing and Evaluations

This study shows the selection of participants and population under purposive sampling method. The respondents of the study are the Grade 7 of Laboratory Science High School of Cavite State University - CCAT campus. The participants will answer a survey questionnaire and two sets of assessments—a diagnostic assessment and summative assessment provided by the researchers.

Research Instruments

The instrument used in this study were the following:

Science Educational Comics

The researcher developed a science educational comic in cell biology. The comics consist of two main topics in cell biology: cell organelles and their functions, and cell division. The content was based on the DepEd Most Essential Learning Competencies for Grade 7.

Test Questionnaire

The researcher developed a 20-item multiple-choice test. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was used to formulate the set of questions, ensuring validity by aligning them with the learning objectives of each topic. Items 1–5 were for analytical thinking, and Items 11–15 focused on reading comprehension questions about

cell organelles and their functions. Additionally, Items 6–10 were for analytical thinking, and Items 16–20 were for reading comprehension related to cell division, including mitosis and meiosis.

Table 1. Test Questionnaire

Lesson	Analytical Thinking	Reading Comprehension
Cell Organelles & Functions	1-5	11-15
Cell Division	6-10	16-20

Total test item = 20

Survey Questionnaire

A 3-item survey questionnaire was created by the researcher, which included questions about the content features, style of the comics, and suggestions for other fields of science that respondents preferred to be included in future science educational comics.

Table 2. Survey Questionnaire

Number of Item	Survey Questions
1	What do you suggest with the content features that are intended to be included in science educational comics under cell biology?
2	Check what you recommend for the visual style that you prefer for science educational comics <input type="checkbox"/> Superhero style <input type="checkbox"/> Manga style <input type="checkbox"/> Cartoon style <input type="checkbox"/> Realistic style <input type="checkbox"/> Caricature style <input type="checkbox"/> Computer-generated imagery Others: _____

- 3 What specific branch of science would you suggest in the next Educational Comics to improve your understanding of abstract concepts?

Research Procedures

The main focus of this study was to evaluate the improvements of the metacognition skills using the science educational comic on students' understanding abstract concept in cell biology. The researcher first obtained a permission letter from the principal of Laboratory Science High School to proceed. This ensured that the researcher and the school administrator agreed before starting the study. Afterward, the following phases were followed:

Phase 1: Pretest

Before using the developed science educational comics in cell biology, the respondents took a 20-item multiple-choice test to assess their initial knowledge of cell biology, focusing on cell function and cell division.

Phase 2: Intervention

After three weeks, the developed science educational comics in cell biology were implemented and used as a learning tool for students. Three comics were distributed to each student, and they were given 1 hour and 30 minutes to read them.

Table 3. Topics of science-based comics

Subject	Lessons	Topics
General Biology 1	Cell Organelles and Functions	Plant Cell & Animal Cells
	Cell Division	Mitosis & Meiosis

Phase 3: Posttest

Once the students finished reading the comics and they were collected by the researcher, the same test questionnaire used in the pretest was administered.

Phase 4: Survey Questionnaire

A survey questionnaire was given afterward to gather recommendations or suggestions on the comics' style, content, features, and potential application in other fields of science for future researchers developing science educational comics.

Data Analysis:

The improvement in metacognitive skills of Grade 7 students in abstract concepts using the developed science educational comics in cell biology was investigated using pre-test and post-test scores from a 20-item multiple-choice test. Item analysis and mean were used to evaluate the gathered data. Item analysis was used to determine the overall mastery level percentage and assess whether students improved in those particular skills. The mean was used to summarize the results of the item analysis and to determine the overall improvement in the metacognitive skills of the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

What lessons in Cell Biology that can be developed into science educational comics

The researchers distributed three science educational comics focused on fundamental lessons in cell biology. The comics include 'Journey to the World of Cell' (cell organelles and their functions), which explores the microscopic world, and 'Mitosis: The Cell Journey' and 'Meiosis: The Power of Four', which highlight real-world applications of mitosis and meiosis.

The settings include a cell and classroom laboratory for organelles, a park for meiosis, and a house and laboratory for mitosis. The main characters, such as Rosalind, Robert, Mei, and Mitz, guide readers through the lessons, offering relatable perspectives on the scientific concepts. Themes such as exploration, discovery, and real-world applications are emphasized in the stories the science or help them relate to the story.

Table 4. Parts Description of Science Educational Comics

Lesson	Title	Theme	Main Characters	Settings	Genre
Cell Organelles and their function	Journey to the World of Cell	Exploration and Discovery	Rosalind Robert	Classroom laboratory, Cell	Science Comics
Mitosis	Mitosis: The Cell Journey	Real-World Applications	Mei Mitz	House, Laboratory	Science Comics
Meiosis	Meiosis: The Power of Four	Real-World Applications	Meimei, Meimei's sibling	Park	Science comics

What is the improvement in the metacognition skills of grade 7 students in Cell Biology

The researchers evaluated the results through item analysis and mean. The item analysis revealed a significant increase in the number of correct answers obtained by the students, rising from 27.6% to 51.8%, with a differential value of +24.2 for analytical thinking. For reading comprehension, the pre-test percentage score increased from 37.3% to 50.4%, with a differential value of +13.1.

Table 5. Summarize Item Analysis

	Item Analysis			Mean Improvement
	Pre-test Results	Post-test Results	Differential	
Metacognition Skills				
Analytical Thinking	27.6%	51.8%	+24.2	+6.7
Reading Comprehension	37.3%	50.4%	+13.1	+2.1

What suggestion on the next content of science educational comics in other field of science

Figure 1 presents data on students' preferred comic styles for science educational comics in cell biology. Most students favored Manga Style (46%), followed by Cartoon Style (36%), highlighting a preference for visually appealing designs with elements of adventure and fantasy.

Figure 1. Comics Styles

The respondents suggested that the content should specify each cell's capabilities, not just their functions, and include other types of cells, like prokaryotic cells, with a more engaging plot. They also recommended using simpler words or acronyms for unfamiliar terms to improve readability. Here are some student comments on content features:

Respondent 1: *"The content is detailed, but the words could be simplified. For example, change 'elucidates' to 'explains.' Some key terms were unclear."*

Respondent 2: *"Include acronyms for unusual words like RNA to make it easier to understand."*

The survey data also revealed that Astronomy was the most preferred field of science for future comics, followed by Physics and Biology. Students suggested exploring planets, stars, celestial bodies, and abstract concepts of the universe.

Here are some student comments on other science fields:

Respondent 1: *"I suggest Astronomy, as it has complex but interesting topics, like black holes and other celestial bodies."*

Respondent 2: *"I'd suggest Astronomy because many students like it, and it would improve my understanding."*

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

Based to the gathered data, the following conclusions were hereby drawn:

1. The researchers developed three science educational comics—"Journey to the World of Cell," "Mitosis: The Cell Journey," and "Meiosis: The Power of Four"—to simplify cell biology concepts by integrating topics on cell organelles, mitosis, and meiosis.
2. The study concluded that the intervention significantly improved grade 7 students' analytical thinking skills by 6.7 points and reading comprehension by 2.1 points, showing greater effectiveness in enhancing analytical thinking.
3. The researcher recommended utilizing science educational comics in other areas of science, such as astronomy, to explore celestial bodies in the universe.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis and results of the data gathered from the participants' recommendations, Grade 7 students from the Laboratory Science High School.

1. The researcher was suggested to use simplify terminologies and key concepts enhancing the reading comprehension and analytical thinking of learners.

2. The researcher suggests that in order to facilitate understanding, incorporating acronyms of each unfamiliar words may reduce confusions.

3. The researcher also suggested to use other type of comics like manga to encourage creativity, and make learning more relatable and enjoyable.

4. The researcher suggested to use educational comics to other branches of science especially astronomy that talks about celestial bodies, planets, stars in the universe.

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